

User Manual: Shiny mirror-App

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Simulation-based investigations of interrater agreement as proposed in Bodner et al. 2023 is a boresome endeavour. To this end, we developed a shiny app(lication) that gives researchers the possibility to test their reported data. In what follows we will shortly describe the application, which is entirely based on the test paradigm as described in the paper. This manual contains additional explications and considerations. We follow in this manual the structure and workflow of the app. The shiny app can be accessed at

<https://gitlab.kuleuven.be/ppw-okpiv/researchers/u0090403/shinymirror> .

User Manual

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Getting started

To run the app, R-studio and the corresponding basic R software need to be installed. Further, the app depends on the packages

- irrCAC,
- irr,
- reshape,
- ggplot2,
- RColorBrewer&
- Shiny

If you want to check whether the packages are installed and install those that are missing, you may run:

```
list.of.packages =  
  c("irrCAC", "irr", "reshape2", "ggplot2", "RColorBrewer", "shiny")  
new.packages = list.of.packages[!(list.of.packages %in%  
  installed.packages()[, "Package"])]  
if(length(new.packages)) install.packages(new.packages)
```

Code 1. Checking whether needed packages are installed and install the missing ones.

Initializing the app

The app can then be started by running the following code:

```
library(shiny)  
shiny::runUrl(  
  https://gitlab.kuleuven.be/ppw-okpiv/researchers/  
  u0090403/shinymirror/-/archive/master/  
  shinymirror-master.tar.gz  
)
```

Code 2. Starting the code

A window will pop up that represents the app (Figure 1). The app contains two panels. The left side panel, where the researchers specify their investigations and needs, and the main panel, where the results are displayed. Both the left side panel and the main panel, are divided into three sections, roughly called: (1) Data, (2) Analysis, (3) Results.

Figure 1. The initial window of the shiny app (before specifying anything).

The three sections of the app represent the three steps that need to be taken to be successful in the investigation of the interrater agreements: First, the data needs to be selected (corresponding to the requirements) and characteristics will be provided by the app. Second, the analysis needs to be specified and the simulation study will be executed and displayed. And finally, the decision parameters for the results need to be specified and the results will be displayed. The same three steps will also guide the exploration of the app in this manual.

Data

Data requirements

The app allows the researcher to read in their data by choosing a dataset from the local device (See Figure 1). The data needs to be saved as an “.Rdata” array. The different time points are depicted in rows. Different raters are represented in the cols next to each other. Reports of different subjects are staged in the third dimension (one after the other). Here it is important to make sure that the different raters’ are always noted in the same column. If, for example, rater 2 and rater 3 rated subject 3, but not rater 1, the column of rater 1 is filled with NAs for subject 3.

Including different variables

The app also allows to process data with different variables. Those can be differentiated in the 4th dimension. Both data with three or four dimensions can be processed by the app. If the data has four dimensions, a menu to choose the variables will pop up (Figure 2).

Output – data descriptives

The app itself will then provide a breve summary of the data (Figure 2). First, the maximal length of the provided time series will be displayed as well as a summary of the deviations. Further, the number of raters (and their names if they are indicated in the data) will be displayed plus how many subject files were double or triple-coded. Also, the range of the relative frequency and the range of the serial dependence will be displayed.

Figure 2. Example of the app window after data specification.

The data set toyexample.R has been chosen by the researcher. As the data set contains 4 dimensions a selection-of-variable panel is opened underneath the data selection window. The characteristics of the original data as provided in the main window of the app.

Analysis and Simulation

The main idea of the simulation-based interrater agreement assessment is to simulate data that resembles the rater-reported data in different respects. As in detail explained in Bodner et al (2023), we use a two-step data generation method. First, we simulate the underlying (in practice unknown) true data accounting for relative frequency and serial dependence. In the second step, we let the fictive raters commit errors. Therefore we generate an error pattern for each rater and apply it to the same true data. The result is a pair/triplet of related time series, on which the interrater agreement measures are calculated. Repeating this procedure over and over again, we get a distribution of simulated interrater agreement values then will later serve as a reference. For the data generation, the researchers can make several specifications: (1) Simulation paradigm, (2) number of raters, (3) number of simulated data pairs/triplets, (4) serial dependence in the error, and finally (5) which interrater agreement measure should be used.

Figure 3. The analysis and simulation part as provided in the app.

The researcher can choose the way of data generation (default: simulate), the number of raters (default: as in provided data), the number of replicates for the test (default: 100), specification of the serial dependence as the length of segments: 1 (no serial dependence; default), 5 (moderate), 10 (substantive), 20 (very strong) and the interrater agreement measures (default: Gwet's AC). The app provides three boxplots corresponding with the distribution for 5.3%, 11.3%, and 18.4%. The vertical lines indicate the values of the interrater agreement calculated on the rater-reported data. The vertical brownish dashed line indicates the 95th quantile of the chosen level.

Simulation paradigm

The app allows specifying, whether the true data should be generated the true data by simulation (default), via a segment-shuffling approach, or by using the original data.

Original. This data generation uses a randomly chosen rater-reported time series as true data. Each rater-reported data can be used several times. This approach is useful if different time series are available, for example, from different individuals. This true data generation mechanism is simple, and quick and keeps other properties of the rater-reported data.

Segment. To augment the variation in the simulated true data, we also included a segmented approach. The rater-reported data is cut into segments and shuffled between

the time series (The first segment of the newly generated true data time series is drawn from all first segments of the rater-reported data, the second one from all second segments, etc.) This approach is specially designed to account for temporal dynamics in the time series (e.g., if an intervention takes place at a specific time point, the generated true data will still contain the imprint of this intervention).

Simulate. The true data can, of course also be simulated. We draw the data time point per time point from a Bernoulli distribution, relying on the frequency, and the conditional probabilities of the rater-reported data. This approach is always possible and leads to a diversified sample.

Number of raters

The app allows to include calculations for two or three raters, default is the most prevalent one in the data. Three raters is default chosen, whenever the data is coded by more than three raters. The default choice can be overruled by a simple tik.

Number of replicates

The researcher can choose how many pairs/triplets of rater data should be generated. (100 default, 200, 500, 1000).

Serial dependence of the error: length of the segments

The app allows the inclusion of serial dependence in the error. It is indeed quite likely that a rater that does not recognize a certain behavior at a given time point also fails to recognize it the next moment. To this end, the app uses a segment shuffling approach. Briefly spoken: the longer the segments, the more likely it is that mistakes follow each other. The app provides the possibility to choose between independence or the error (default; a segment of the length 1), moderate (length of 5), strong (length of 10), and very strong (length of 20).

Interrater agreement measure

The rater may choose between Fleiss' Kappa, Gwet's AC (default), and Brennan Prediger.

Simulation

The rater data is generated by implementing error with fixed error rates of 5.3%, 11.3%, and 18.4%. This corresponds with "almost perfect", "substantial" and "moderate" interrater agreement. Finally, on the simulated pairs/triplets of rater data the interrater agreement is calculated. The different horizontal boxplots in the mid-panel of the app display the distributions that correspond to the different levels of agreement. The values calculated on the "original" rater-reported data are represented as vertical black lines, each line representing one subject.

Results

Finally, also the level of desired agreement can be chosen out of almost perfect (implementing an error rate of 5.3%), substantial (11.3%), and moderate (18.4%). The 95th quantile of the distribution of the contingency measure on the simulated data corresponding to the chosen agreement level is depicted as a brownish dashed line (Figure 3). The app also returns the exact value of the threshold (brownish dashed line) and indicates which subjects (if the subjects were named in the file) would have a value that is significantly higher than assumed with a certain error rate (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. The results section as provided in the app
The researcher can choose the agreement level (almost perfect; substantial default; or moderate). The app accordingly shows which data is sufficiently well-rated and which is not.

References:

Bodner et al. (2023). A simulation-based test to investigate interrater agreement for binary time series. [Unpublished manuscript]. Psychology and Educational sciences. KU Leuven.